

Synthesis of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ thin film by RF-magnetron sputtering for solar cell applications

V.Parthibaraj, K.S. Pugazhivadivu, C. Rangasami and K. Tamilarasan*

Department of physics, Kongu Engineering College, Perundurai – 638060, Erode, Tamil nadu, India
Email: dr.k.tamilarasan@gmail.com, 9842966128

Abstract

Polycrystalline $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ (CZTS) thin films have been grown on Mo coated glass substrate by RF-magnetron sputtering at substrate temperatures of 573 K, 623 K, 673 K and 723 K. Structural and optical properties of the grown thin films have been investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscope (SEM), Raman spectroscopy and UV-vis spectroscopy. Detailed analysis of XRD data is shown that the grown CZTS thin film has kieselite structure ($a = 5.4290$ and $c = 10.849\text{\AA}$) with preferred orientation along (112) plane. All the peaks observed in the XRD pattern have been accounted for kieselite structure, which shows the absence of additional phases such as elemental or binary or ternary systems in the grown film. SEM images recorded with different magnification have showed that the film has smooth and homogeneous surface with average crystallite size 120 nm. Raman spectrum recorded at room temperature which conveys that the dominant Raman shift at 326 cm^{-1} can be attributed to A1 mode and confirms the formation of kieselite CZTS phase. From optical transmittance spectrum, the grown film is found to have direct band gap of $\sim 1.51\text{ eV}$. The above observations show that the material under investigation is suitable for solar cell application.

Keywords: $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$; RF magnetron sputtering; Optical band gap.

References

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